

CHALLENGES IN THE REPLACEMENT OF EPS PACKAGING WITH THE BIOBASED ONE IN A LARGE SCALE PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENT

Aleš Mihelič¹, Boris Šmon¹, Radoje Radojčić¹, Vekoslav Matanović¹, Blaž Starc¹, Anton Chechotkin¹ Gregor Čepon²

¹Gorenje d.o.o., Slovenia

²Univerza v Ljubljani, Fakulteta za strojništvo, Slovenia

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ales.mihelic@gorenje.com

Abstract: *The environment and sustainable behavior is in modern society increasingly important topic. The white goods producers have made in the last decade significant effort to reduce the energy consumption of the home appliances, a little less attention was made to the recyclability of products and packaging. Today plastics components of the home appliances and EPS packaging and foil is predominately made from fossil oil. In Gorenje location in Velenje in 2022 astounding 2.200 tons of EPS was used only for packaging. Out of this 57% was used for packaging of kitchen appliances, 25% for laundry appliances and 18% for dishwashers. The EU green deal and connected sustainable product initiative and the legislation adopted puts a lot of pressure on the Gorenje predevelopment and category packaging teams to come with more sustainable packaging option. The challenges in the implementation were threefold: technical due to large impact forces that can with the heaviest appliances easy overcome 100 g; organisational, where solution has to be easy to implement and must allow gradual transitioning; technical capabilities of the paper packaging suppliers. All these aspects will be presented in the article, demonstrating difficulties in the company sustainable packaging transitioning.*

Keywords: sustainability, packaging, white goods, cushioning

1 INTRODUCTION

The environment and sustainable behaviour is in modern society increasingly important topic. The white goods producers have made in the last decade significant effort to reduce the energy consumption of the home appliances, a little less attention was made to the recyclability of products and packaging. Today plastics components of the home appliances and EPS (expanded polystyrene) and foil is predominately made from fossil oil.

The EU Green deal and the proposal for a new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), published in March 2022, is the cornerstone of the EU Commission's approach to more environmentally sustainable and circular products. The proposal establishes a framework to set eco-design requirements for specific product groups to significantly improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects. It sets the performance and information requirements for almost all categories of physical goods placed on the EU market.

The framework will allow for the setting of a wide range of requirements, including on:

- product durability, reusability, upgradability, and reparability
- presence of substances that inhibit circularity
- energy and resource efficiency
- recycled content
- remanufacturing and recycling
- carbon and environmental footprints
- information requirements, including a Digital Product Passport

The incoming regulations and the legislative proposals of Australia, France and United Kingdom, where tis countries plan to ban, restrict or heavily tax the usage of oil-based EPS for packaging after 2025 puts a lot of pressure on the producers of different goods to shift towards more sustainable packaging solutions.

The white goods producers have made in the last decade significant effort to reduce the energy consumption of the home appliances, a little less attention was made to the recyclability of products and packaging. Today plastics components of the home appliances and EPS packaging and foil is predominately made from fossil oil. In Hisense Europe company Gorenje only in Velenje location in 2022 astounding 2.200 tons of EPS was used only for packaging. Out of this 57% was used for packaging of kitchen appliances, 25% for laundry appliances and 18% for dishwashers.

In the present paper the challenges in the replacement of EPS packaging with the biobased one are explained more in detail (Kun et al., 2017; Andena et al., 2018).

2 EPS PACKAGING REPLACEMENT CHALLENGES

2.1 Available options study

At the beginning of the project the overview of possible options was performed. It is obvious that the biobased alternatives offer more sustainable and eco-friendly options than EPS, which commonly known as Styrofoam, and is widely used packaging material, but it is not environmentally friendly as it is non-biodegradable and can persist in the environment for hundreds of years. Here are some potential biobased replacement options:

1. **Biodegradable Polymers:** Materials like polylactic acid (PLA), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), and polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) can be used as substitutes for EPS. These biodegradable polymers are derived from renewable sources such as corn starch or sugarcane, and they can break down naturally in the environment.
2. **Mushroom Packaging:** Mycelium, the root structure of mushrooms, can be used to create biodegradable packaging materials. It's grown on agricultural waste, making it both biobased and biodegradable. Mushroom packaging is strong and can replace EPS in various applications.
3. **Paper-Based Packaging:** Traditional paper packaging is biodegradable and can be used as a replacement for EPS in many applications. Additionally, advanced paper-based materials, like corrugated cardboard, can offer sufficient protection for fragile items.
4. **Bioplastics:** Bioplastics are plastics derived from renewable sources, such as starch, cellulose, or algae. Some bioplastics, like polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), can serve as alternatives to EPS in various packaging applications.
5. **Agricultural Residues:** Agricultural waste products like wheat straw, rice husks, or cornstarch can be used to create biobased packaging materials. These materials are not only renewable but can also be composted or biodegraded.
6. **Seaweed-Based Packaging:** Seaweed-derived materials, like agar or alginate, have been explored as biobased packaging options. They are abundant in the ocean and can be used for single-use packaging solutions.

7. **Recycled Paperboard:** Using recycled paper and cardboard for packaging is an environmentally friendly alternative. These materials can often be recycled again after use.
8. **Edible Packaging:** Edible packaging materials made from ingredients like rice, potatoes, or tapioca can replace EPS for certain food packaging applications. Consumers can either consume the packaging or compost it.
9. **Plant-Based Foams:** Some companies have developed foam-like materials from plants like cornstarch or soybeans. These materials can be used for cushioning and insulating purposes in packaging.
10. **Biodegradable Air Pillows:** Instead of traditional EPS-filled air pillows for cushioning, biodegradable alternatives made from materials like PLA or PBAT are available.

When considering biobased alternatives to EPS, it's essential to assess the specific application, considering factors such as durability, cost, and end-of-life options (e.g., composting or recycling). Sustainable packaging solutions often involve a combination of these materials and a thoughtful approach to reduce waste and environmental impact.

Based on all above-mentioned arguments and availability of the ready industrialized solutions we have decided to continue our research with the paper based biodegradable solutions.

2. 2 First tests with corrugated cardboard

The first idea was to replace the EPS packaging with the corrugated cardboard. After first few transport tests on the testing facility, it was clear that the corrugated cardboard is not a viable solution for heavier home appliances like washing machines and tumble driers. The multiple impact accelerations that the relatively thin cardboard packaging must withstand exceed 100 g. The results of the test were completely damaged home appliances.

2. 3 Entering in the uncharted waters

It was clear from the first tests that Trial and error method will take too much time and will be too expensive due to large number of experiments needed and resulting in the large number of damaged and destroyed appliances. The obvious solution was to do the test on digital twins (Lye et al., 2004; Kun et al., 2017). But for this you need a number of material characteristics which were not available. Therefore, the main challenge was to get paper packaging properties that would

allow us the numerical simulation of the cushioning properties. By this we have made paper construction material where we can simulate dynamic behavior.

Fortunately, the Gorenje Predevelopment department was already working on the research of the biobased packaging solution for the washing machines in cooperation with the Faculty of mechanical engineering in Ljubljana (Mihelič et al., 2023).

The first obstacle was to build the test site and determine the standard measurement procedure. It showed that the ASTM D1596 standard, could help the team to get needed material and cushioning properties of different cushioning materials and especially the cardboard and paper honeycomb.

Figure 1. Testing equipment to determine the cushioning properties of the cardboard and paper honeycomb.

The following tests performed at the Faculty of mechanical engineering in Ljubljana:

- Measurement of damping curves
 - Vertical damping
 - Horizontal damping
- Dependence from contact surface/ static pressure

took us more than one month. Anyway, the performed tests provide the necessary data which enable us to use the mechanical and dynamical properties in the digital twins of the packaging.

Figure 2. Testing equipment to determine the cushioning properties of the cardboard and paper honeycomb.

The main conclusion of the test was the curve which demonstrate the ability of different cushioning materials to withstand multiple impact force (Fadiji et al., 2018).

Figure 3. Cushioning characteristics of different materials after multiple impacts.

2. 4 Packaging design

Based on the knowledge gained by material testing then the tedious work of designing the packaging for different home appliances begins. In the continuation there are some pictures that represent some of the digital twin design testing. The digital twins performed quite well, since we manage to reduce dramatically the number of need physical transportation tests. In majority of cases the first physical test was nearly OK, then some smaller modifications of the packaging design on the critical parts was perform. In one case there was a large scatter of the test results, which puzzled the team. At the end it showed that it was not problem in packaging but that the design of tested appliance needed some modifications to be more resilient to extreme transportation forces and accelerations (Čepon et al., 2021).

Figure4: Numerical simulation examples

Figure 5. Design of tumble dryer cardboard and honeycomb packaging.

3 TESTING OF THE BIOBASED PACKAGING SOLUTION

Gorenje is selling their home appliances all over the world. In recent years the trend is more and more changing away from large retailers, but we observe that the transport goes through several warehouses where different transporting and manipulation facilities are used.

Therefore, the test procedures that appliances and packaging has to withstand are relatively strict and are composed of following procedure and tests:

1. Test on min. 2 packaged test samples
2. Transportation tests: lateral compression test, stacking test, vibration test, free fall test – 5 drops, impact test (slope) on all 4 sides, reload test.
3. Unpackaging and inspecting samples after completed tests
4. Additional test in moisture chamber for overseas transport

The development work of a large team of colleagues working on the design and improve of packaging resulted in biobased design of packaging for all Gorenje home appliance products that withstand strict transport regulations.

The only issue that is partially solved is the moisture resistance. The designed packaging can easily withstand the oversee transport in containers and relatively humid environment. The difficulty is in the warehouses and transport means

where they left appliances standing in the water, so the cardboard has the time to absorb the water, and by this losing a lot of its cushioning properties. For mentioned cases the team manage to find a solution for bottom cover, which is unfortunately not biodegradable, but it is 100% recyclable and reusable and has a good water resistance.

4 INDUSTRIALISATION

With the proof of concept that the paper based biodegradable packaging is a suitable replacement for the existing EPS packaging the industrialization phase begins. In this phase the Gorenje experts need to do the following steps:

- The qualified suppliers have to be found for honeycomb and corrugated cardboard
- Adapt with the producer's manufacturability requests
- Test the assembly on the production line
- Repeat the tests to prove the quality
- Approve the samples
- Negotiating the prices and other conditions
- Adopt Gorenje standard for honeycomb cardboard packaging to ensure the quality of subsequent deliveries.

In the process of industrialization Gorenje has discussion with different suppliers of corrugated cardboard and paper honeycomb. It was interesting to see that the large majority of suppliers are only available to provide results on Trial and error method. They are more focus on the esthetic design and rely mainly on their experiences. We have seen that the usage of digital twins to actually calculate the material properties need for the adequate protection is really novel in the paper making industry.

This process of industrialization is still taking place in Gorenje and we are progressing product by product. The adoption of the biodegradable packaging in the regular production is also dependent on the category, negotiated prices and market demand. Some appliances like hood in hob, gas hobs, RedBull refrigerators, induction plates, under counter wine chiller are already having paper packaging. The rest are to be introduced during the year 2023 and 2024.

5 FURTHER RESEARCH TO IMPROVE EVEN MORE THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

During the two-year development and industrialization phase we have seen that there is only relatively little number of suppliers of paper honeycomb in Europe. This means that the logistic has very strong environmental impact, since the honeycomb has a large volume filled with air. One of the suppliers has also offered a solution that we can assemble honeycomb on site, which involves relatively high investment and production space requirement.

Anyway, in R&D we have also started research of alternative paper-based solutions that will have even lower environmental impact. We were lucky to get co-financing of LEAP project through the Norwegian fund mechanism to explore the cast pulp solutions from invasive plants.

6 CONCLUSION

The work of the group was successful as we have demonstrated that cardboard packaging with paper honeycomb inserts if properly designed is a suitable eco-friendly solution for all categories: washing machines, tumble dryers, dishwashers, ovens, induction and gas hobs, hoods, hood in hob, refrigerators, and wine chillers.

From the Gorenje journey it was clear that large companies with enough R&D capabilities can make this transition. The situation is much more complex for the small sized companies, where more support will be needed from the paper industry or specialized centers that will help the transitioning from EPS to bio-based packaging.

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